

The Role of Service Quality and Perceived Value on Word of Mouth for E-Commerce Application Users

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to determine and analyze the effect of service quality on satisfaction in the use of Shopee, the effect of service quality on trust in the use of Shopee, the effect of perceived value on trust in the use of Shopee, the effect of perceived value on loyalty in the use of Shopee, the effect of satisfaction on WOM in the use of Shopee, the effect of trust on WOM in the use of Shopee. The influence of loyalty to WOM in the use of Shopee. The results showed four accepted hypotheses, while the other three were rejected. The first hypothesis is accepted, namely that service quality has a direct and significant effect on satisfaction. While the second hypothesis is accepted, service quality has a significant direct effect on trust.

1. Introduction

The fourth industrial revolution today is closely related to technological advances and the internet. Both will affect consumer behavior in goods and services markets (Sima et al., 2020). The actors involved in the cycle of buying and selling goods and services will have a closer distance due to advances in technology and the internet. The emergence of various places of buying and selling on the internet results from advances in technology and the internet.

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Figure 1. Online Trading Data in Indonesia in 2021

Source: Hootsuite(2021). Accessed in November 2021.

The figure above shows data on trade in goods that use the internet in Indonesia in 2021. The figure shows that almost one-third of Indonesian people are buying and selling using the internet, 30 billion USD transactions in e-commerce, 49 percent growth in the value of e-commerce, and the average customer spends 219 USD on making purchases using the internet(Hootsuite, 2021).

The magnitude of the transaction value and the number of Indonesian people who use the internet as a means of buying and selling cannot be separated from the increasing number of new internet-based businesses. The Central Bureau of Statistics noted that 45.93 percent of new businesses started operating in 2017-2019 (Statistics, 2020). However, the increase in transactions that occur in internet-based businesses is inversely proportional to offline businesses or traders who have physical stalls. According to Jonathan (Aisyah Kamaliah, 2021), offline business transactions declined by 34% in 2021. One of the factors that caused this decline was the shift of buyers from offline stores to online stores. Even so, offline merchants who have fewer buyers still stick to offline stores for various reasons (Efrem Siregar, 2019).

#	APP NAME	PARENT COMPANY
1	TIKTOK	BYTENDANCE
2	FACEBOOK	FACEBOOK
3	WHATSAPP	FACEBOOK
4	INSTAGRAM	FACEBOOK
5	SHOPEE	SEA
6	TELEGRAM	TELEGRAM
7	ZOOM	ZOOM VIDEO COM
8	FACEBOOK MESSENGER	FACEBOOK
9	SNACK VIDEO	ONESMILE
10	SHAREIT	SHAREIT

Figure 1. Application Mobile Downloads Ranking

Source: Hootsuite(2021). Accessed in November 2021.

One of the most popular online shopping sites or online marketplaces in Indonesia is Shopee. Based on the picture above(Hootsuite, 2021), Shopee is the fifth-ranked application with the most

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downloads in Indonesia. Shopee downloads come under four social media apps. This means that Shopee is the most downloaded online shopping application by the people of Indonesia. Shopee is a marketplace in Singapore established in 2015 (Anggraini et al., 2018). Shopee has expanded its reach to countries such as Indonesia, Singapore, Malaysia, Thailand, Vietnam, the Philippines, and Taiwan (Anggraini et al., 2018). Shopee claims to be the first mobile platform in Southeast Asia and Taiwan that offers fun, free, and reliable online buying and selling transactions (Indonesia, 2019).

Shopee Indonesia acts as an intermediary between sellers and buyers by making it easier for users to find the items they want to buy. Starting from electronic devices, household needs, accessories, clothing, etc. Shopee also offers various payment options. Transfer payments through banks and mini markets, and pay on the spot to create your payment options in the form of Shopeepay. In Indonesia, Shopee often carries out massive promotions and discounts. One promotional tool that Shopee is an endorsement of Indonesian and even foreign public figures (Ode et al., 2020). The purpose of endorsements is to increase a product's or brand's good impression in customers' minds (Chen & Lin, 2018). Endorsement by Shopee creates a promotional technique called word of mouth (WOM). Wu et al. (2018) explained that WOM is a promotional technique that is more likely to rely on experienced customers' recommendations before buying because online services are more intangible and more difficult to evaluate.

Figure 3. Primary Channels for Brand Research

Source: Hootsuite(2021). Accessed in November 2021.

Figure 4. Sources of New Brand Discovery

Source: Hootsuite(2021). Accessed in November 2021.

Based on the two pictures above, consumer reviews and recommendations or comments on social media, included in WOM, are ranked third as a channel to describe a brand image in Indonesia.(YK Choi et al., 2017; Hootsuite, 2021; Reyes-Menendez et al., 2019). WOM behavior on consumers will be influenced by satisfaction (satisfaction), trust (trust), and loyalty (loyalty)(Hassan et al., 2018; Jung & Seock, 2017; Mukerjee, 2018).

2. Materials and Methods

To answer the research problem regarding the effect of satisfaction, trust, and loyalty on WOM on Shopee application users, causal associative research using a quantitative approach is used. This type of research is explanatory research using surveys and technical data analysis SEM (Structural Equation Modeling). The technique of obtaining data for this study is by distributing questionnaires containing questions and/or statements to respondents. The questionnaire in this study used Microsoft Forms media which was distributed online through social media WhatsApp, Twitter, and Instagram.

Validity test

According to Uma Sekaran and Bougie(2013), the validity test is a test of research instruments developed with certain steps to measure certain variables. This validity test is used to test the accuracy of the data in the questionnaire, which will then become the primary data in a study. In this study, the validity test was carried out by testing the Explanatory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). Explanatory Factor Analysis is a factor analysis method to identify the relationship between variables, while Confirmatory Factor Analysis is an analytical method used to test good indicators in describing a number of construct factors (Hair et al., 2010). The minimum number of factor loading in this study is 0.6 for EFA and 0.05 for CFA(Hair et al., 2010).

Reliability Test

According to Sekaran and Bougie(2013), reliability is a way of testing how consistent the concept of the measuring instrument is. The reference for this reliability test is Cronbach alpha (α) from variable data analysis. Cronbach alpha (α) is an illustration of how much a factor is related between one variable and another. A variable with a value of Cronbach alpha (α) with a value below 0.07 is considered unreliable, and a value of Cronbach alpha (α) with a value above 0.07 is considered reliable. (Sekaran & Bougie, 2013).

Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing in this study is a causal model or causality using the Structural Equation Models (SEM) technique with AMOS. SEM in this study aims to identify the dimensions of a construct and measure the influence of the factors whose dimensions have been identified. (Ferdinand, 2002). SEM analysis techniques used in this study include:

1. Confirmatory factor analysis aims to confirm the most dominant factors in a variable.
2. Regression (Regression Weight) is used to examine how much the variables influence each other on other variables.

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According to Haryono and Wardoyo(2012), there are five stages to using Structural Equation Models (SEM), namely:

1. Model Specification

The theoretical mode specification is the first step to be described in a diagrammatic form, making it easier for researchers to see the causality relationships they want to test. At this stage, the researcher will define the construct conceptually under study and determine its dimensionality. After this, the direction of cause and effect between one variable and another will show a relationship that produces a hypothesis with a strong foundation.

2. Model Identification

The second stage is the identification of the research model. The purpose of identifying the research model is to find out whether the model built with empirical data has a unique value or not so that the model can be estimated. If the model has a unique value, it cannot be identified by AMOS.

3. Model Estimation

The purpose of the estimation phase of this model is to obtain the values of the parameters in the model. The model estimation technique used in SEM AMOS is Maximum Likelihood Estimation.

4. Match Test

The analysis process in the SEM method requires a Goodness of Fit (GOF) model fit test stage in order to get a fitness model in accordance with the sample data. Some of the criteria for the size of the fit can use several steps, namely:

A. Chi-square

The first statistic and the only statistical test in GOF are χ^2 . The researcher tries to obtain a low Chi-square (χ^2) value which results in a significance level > 0.05 or ($p > 0.05$), which indicates that the null hypothesis is accepted.

B. The goodness of Fit Index (GFI)

GFI can be classified as an absolute fit measure because it compares the hypothesized model with no model ($\sum(\theta)$). The GFI value ranges from 0 (poor fit) to 1 (perfect fit), and a GFI value > 0.90 is a good fit, while $0.80 < \text{GFI} < 0.90$ is often referred to as marginal fit.

C. CMIN/DF

Minimum Sample Discrepancy Function divided by the Degree of Freedom. The chi-square statistic χ^2 divided by DF with the result $\chi^2 < 2.0$ means that there is a match between the model and the data.

D. Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA).

RMSEA value < 0.05 indicates close fit, while $0.05 < \text{RMSEA} < 0.08$ indicates good fit.

E. Tucker-Lewis Index / Non-Normed Fit Index (TLI/NNFI)

The TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index) was first proposed as a means to evaluate factor analysis which was later extended to SEM. TLI values ranged from 0 to 1.0, with TLI values > 0.90 indicating good fit and $0.80 < \text{TLI} < 0.90$ being marginal fit.

F. Comparative Fit Index (CFI).

The CFI value will range from 0 to 1. A CFI value > 0.90 indicates good fit, while $0.80 < \text{CFI} < 0.90$ is often referred to as marginal fit.

Table 3
The goodness of Fit Size Comparison

GOF Index	Cut of Value
Chi-square Significant Probability	Expected small 0.05

GIF	0.90
AGFI	0.90
CFI	0.95
TLI/NNFI	0.95
CMIN/DF	2.00
RMSEA	0.80

5. Model Modification

After evaluating the model, evaluating the GOF, and finding the tested model is not fit, it is necessary to modify the model. Modification of the model in the AMOS program can be done by looking at the output of the Modification Index.

The following is the initial model for this research which is processed using AMOS 26.0 software.

Figure 5 Research Model processed with AMOS

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2022

3. Results and Discussions

Results of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Analysis

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) with AMOS

At the CFA stage, which is processed through AMOS, the author conveys the measurements and indicators that exist in this study.

Figure 6. Initial Research Model

Source: Processed primary data, 2022.

Figure 6 above describes the initial research model. The first result is that CMIN shows that the model does not yet have a fit model with a standard P value > 0.05 and CMIN/DF 2.00.

Table 1
CMIN Output On Early Model

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Default Model	102	858,793	362	0.000	2,372
Saturated Model	464	0.000	0		
Independence Model	58	6438,061	406	0.000	15,857

Source: Questionnaire data that has been processed by SPSS 26 in 2022.

Table 1 above shows that this research model does not meet predetermined standards. Thus, the authors modified the indications for the modification indices by eliminating SQ1, SQ2, SQ4, SQ6, S2, S4, T1, T4, T5, L1, L2, PV3, WOM1, and WOM4. After reducing these indicators, the authors carried out modeling in the study with the remaining indicators in accordance with Figure 4.7 below.

Figure 7. Model Modification

Source: Processed primary data, 2022.

Based on Figure 7 above represents the output of the fit model after being modified by the researcher. Thus, this has met the requirements as determined through the CFA, namely the P value > 0.05 and CMIN/DF 2.00 and as shown in Table 2 below, namely:

Table 2

CMIN Model Fit results

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Default Model	63	108,619	89	0.077	1,220
Saturated Model	152	0.000	0		
Independence Model	32	3023,839	120	0.000	25,199

Source: Processed Questionnaire Data, 2022.

Table 2 above represents that the overall estimated value has met the standard, and the CMIN model can be declared fit.

The goodness of Fit Index Analysis

Based on the standard values that have been determined in the research method, the results of the analysis are following the Goodness of Fit index in Table 3 as follows:

Table 3
The goodness of Fit Analysis Results

GOF size	Limit Value	Score	Decision
CMIN/DF	2.00	1.234	<i>Good Fit</i>
GFI	0.90	0.955	<i>Good Fit</i>
RMR	0.05	0.027	<i>Good Fit</i>
RMSEA	0.05	0.028	<i>Close Fit</i>
NFI	0.90	0.867	<i>Good Fit</i>
AGFI	0.90	0.934	<i>Good Fit</i>
IFI	0.90	0.993	<i>Good Fit</i>
CFI	0.90	0.993	<i>Good Fit</i>
TLI	0.90	0.991	<i>Good Fit</i>

Source: Processed Questionnaire Data, 2022.

Based on Table 3 above, the authors can make a match in accordance with the AMOS research as follows, namely:

- 1) *The goodness of Fit Index* (GFI) = 0.955; Based on this value, the model is declared a good fit.
- 2) *Root Mean Square Error* (RMR) = 0.027; Based on this value, the model is declared a good fit.
- 3) CMIN/DF = 1.234; This shows that the model can be received well.
- 4) *Root Mean Square Error of Approximation* (RMSEA) = 0.028; RMSEA value indicates that the result is a close fit.
- 5) *Normal Fit Index* (NFI) = 0.867; indicates that the model is a good fit.
- 6) *Adjusted Goodness Fit of Index* (AGFI) = 0.934; based on these values, it is stated that the model is a good fit.
- 7) *Incremental Fit Index* (IFI) = 0.993; indicates that the model is marginally fit.
- 8) *Comparative Fit Index* (CFI) = 0.993; so that based on this value it is declared good fit.
- 9) *Tucker-Lewis Index* (TLI) = 0.991; Based on this value, it is stated that the model is a good fit.

Based on the results of the analysis on the Goodness of Fit index above, it can be seen that all of the criteria have met the Goodness of Fit.

Discussion of the Results of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Analysis

SEM analysis of the AMOS application shows that this research model meets nine criteria for the Goodness of Fit index, namely GFI, RMR, CMIN/DF, RMSEA, NFI, AGFI, IFI, CFI, and TLI. Based on the table of output results that has been shown previously, it shows that the GFI value is 0.973. This value states that the research model is declared a good fit. Thus, successfully exceeding the value that has become the limit in the determined index assessment.

While the RMR value is 0.028. The limit value determined to get a good fit model is less than 0.05. Because the resulting value is below 0.05, the value of the research model is declared a good fit. This is in line with the CMIN/DF value of 1.234 with a set standard of less than 2.00. The next analysis is about the RMSEA value with a value of 0.028. From these results, it is stated that the value is in the close fit value range. The RMSEA value is declared close fit when the RMSEA value is 0.05.

The NFI value is 0.867. The AGFI value is 0.954. The IFI value is 0.993 and the CFI is 0.993, while the TLI value is 0.991. With the condition that the good fit for each standard is more than 0.90. This is because all requirements are met for each standard, so the research model is declared a good fit for the overall assessment standard.

Hypothesis Test Results

The hypothesis has a significance value using a standard value of 1.96 but also has a P value <0.05, while the strength of the influence is shown in the estimation table based on Generalized Least Squares Estimates in Appendix 4, so the research hypothesis test is presented in Table 4 below:

Table 4
Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	Estimate	SE	CR	P
SQ→S	1.073	0.101	10,611	***
SQ→T	1.068	0.114	9,370	***
PV→T	0.019	0.067	0.278	0.781
PV→L	0.931	0.080	11,601	***
L→WOM	0.723	0.070	10,320	***
T→WOM	0.406	0.270	1,505	0.132
S→WOM	0.073	0.294	0.248	0.804

Source: Processed Questionnaire Data, 2022.

In addition, the coefficient of determination or r-square test was also carried out. The following are the results of the coefficient of determination test through the SPSS application in Table 5 below:

Table 5
Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R-Square
X1, X2→Y1	0.665
X1, X2→Y2	0.631

$$\frac{X1, X2 \rightarrow Y3}{0.527}$$

Source: Processed Questionnaire Data, 2022.

Information:

X1 = SQ

X2 = PV

Y1 = S

Y2 = T

Y3 = L

Discussion of Hypothesis Test Results

Based on Table 6, it can be concluded that the results of hypothesis testing are as follows:

Table 6
Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	Estimate	SE	CR	P	Information
SQ→S	1.073	0.101	10,611	***	Received
SQ→T	1.068	0.114	9,370	***	Received
PV→T	0.019	0.067	0.278	0.781	Rejected
PV→L	0.931	0.080	11,601	***	Received
S→WOM	0.073	0.294	0.248	0.804	Rejected
T→WOM	0.406	0.270	1,505	0.132	Rejected
L→WOM	0.723	0.070	10,320	***	Received

Source: Processed Questionnaire Data, 2022.

Table 6 above represents that the first hypothesis is that service quality has a significant direct effect on satisfaction. This statement is in accordance with previous research (Rita et al., 2019; Sureshchandar et al., 2002; Taylor & Baker, 1994; Wang & Shieh, 2006; Zeise et al., 2001), which shows the influence of service quality and satisfaction. The CR value is 10,611 and is above the limit, and the P value is also accepted. This study shows that service quality is a very important factor in determining Shopee user satisfaction in Greater Jakarta. The quality of services provided by Shopee is successful in increasing user satisfaction. Thus, this study shows that the quality of service provided by Shopee will affect the level of user satisfaction.

Because the first hypothesis is accepted, it can be seen that Shopee users recognize Shopee's service quality, which will directly impact user satisfaction. So, it can be seen that the quality of Shopee's services can affect and even increase user satisfaction. In addition, it can be seen that the indicator that has the highest value on the service quality factor is SQ1 (Overall, my purchasing experience on the Shopee app was very good.). At the same time, the indicator with the highest satisfaction factor value is S2 (Shopee is getting closer to merchants who use it).

The second hypothesis shows that there is a significant direct effect of service quality on trust. This statement is in accordance with previous research from Eisingerich and Bell (2008), Chenet et al. (2010), Saleem et al. (2017), Science (2018), and Rita et al. (2019), which shows the influence of service quality and trust. The CR value is 9.370 and is above the limit, and the P value is also accepted. This study shows that service quality is a very important factor in increasing the trust of Shopee users in Jabodetabek. The quality of services provided by Shopee has succeeded in increasing user trust. Thus, this study shows that the quality of services provided by Shopee can increase the trust of users.

Because the second hypothesis is accepted, it can be seen that Shopee users recognize Shopee's service quality, which will directly impact user trust. So, it can be seen that the quality of Shopee's services can affect and even increase the trust of its users. In addition, it can be seen that the indicator that has the highest value on the service quality factor is SQ1 (Overall, my purchasing experience on the Shopee app is very good). At the same time, the indicator that has the highest value on the trust factor is T5 (Shopee operates carefully).

The third hypothesis shows the result that perceived value does not have a significant direct effect on trust. This statement contradicts previous research from Chenet et al. (2010), Kamtarin (2012), Hasan et al. (2014), Ponte et al. (2015), and Sharma and Klein (2020). In this study, there is a CR value that is below the limit of 0.278, and the P value is also above the limit of 0.781; therefore, it does not produce a significant value. So it can be concluded that the perception of value from users may not necessarily affect trust in using Shopee.

Because the third hypothesis is rejected, it can result in no direct and significant effect on the perceived value on trust. In addition, it can be seen that the indicator that has the highest value on the perceived value factor is PV2 (Compared to alternative e-commerce, Shopee billed me well). In contrast, the indicator with the highest trust factor value is T5 (Shopee operates carefully).

The fourth hypothesis shows that there is a significant direct effect of perceived value on loyalty. This statement is in accordance with previous research from Yang and Peterson (2004), Brown (2006), Gounaris et al. (2007), Jiang et al. (2016), and Mukerjee (2018), which shows an influence on perceived value and loyalty. The CR value is 11,601 and is above the limit, and the P value is also accepted. This study shows that perceived value is a very important factor in increasing Shopee user loyalty in Jabodetabek. The perceived value gain gained by the user is successful in increasing user loyalty. Thus, this study shows that perceived value given by users can increase user loyalty.

Since this fourth hypothesis is accepted, it can be seen that the perceived value of Shopee users can make them more loyal, which will directly impact user loyalty. So, it can be seen that the perception of Shopee user value can influence and even increase the loyalty of its users. In addition, it can be seen that the indicator that has the highest value on the perceived value is PV2 (Compared to alternative e-commerce, Shopee billed me well). While the indicator that has the highest value on the loyalty factor is L1 (When choosing the same product category, I consider Shopee my first choice).

The fifth hypothesis shows the result that satisfaction does not have a significant direct effect on WOM. This statement contradicts previous research from Files and Prices (1992), Maxham (2001), Laroche et al. (2005), Wangenheim and Bayón (2007), Zhang (2010), and Jung and Seock (2017). In this study, there is a CR value that is below the limit, namely 0.248 and the P value is also above the limit of 0.804. Therefore, it does not produce a significant value. So, it can be concluded that positive satisfaction may not necessarily make them want to promote Shopee to other people through word of mouth.

Because the fifth hypothesis is rejected, it can result in no direct and significant effect on satisfaction of WOM. In addition, it can be seen that the indicator that has the highest score on the satisfaction factor is S2 (Shopee is getting closer to merchants who use it). While the indicator that

has the highest value on the WOM factor is WOM1 (I am willing to recommend Shopee and its products to others).

The sixth hypothesis shows that trust does not have a significant direct effect on WOM. This statement contradicts previous research from Awad and Ragowsky(2008), Kim et al.(2009), Hajli et al.(2014), Jalilvand et al.(2017), and Hassan et al.(2018). In this study, there is a CR value that is below the limit, namely 1.505 and the P value is also above the limit of 0.132. Therefore, it does not produce a significant value. So, it can be concluded that positive user trust may not necessarily make them want to promote Shopee to other people through word of mouth.

Because the sixth hypothesis is rejected, it can result in no direct and significant influence on trust on WOM. In addition, it can be seen that the indicator with the highest trust factor value is T5 (Shopee operates carefully). While the indicator with the highest value on the WOM factor is WOM1 (I am willing to recommend Shopee and its products to others).

The seventh hypothesis shows a significant direct influence on loyalty to WOM. This statement is following previous research from Wangenheim and Bayón(2007), Liao et al.(2010), Choi and Choi(2014), Salehnia et al.(2014), and Mukerjee(2018) which shows an influence on loyalty and WOM. The CR value is 10.320 and is above the limit, and the P value is also accepted. This study shows that loyalty is a very important in supporting users in Jabodetabek to promote Shopee by word of mouth. User loyalty makes users do word-of-mouth promotions. Thus, this study shows that user loyalty makes them want to do promotions to others by word of mouth.

Since the seventh hypothesis is accepted, it can be seen that the loyalty of Shopee users has a direct impact, making them want to do word of mouth promotions. In addition, it can be seen that the indicator with the highest loyalty factor value is L1 (When choosing the same product category, I consider Shopee my first choice). At the same time, the indicator that has the highest value on the WOM factor is WOM1 (I am willing to recommend Shopee and its products to others).

4. Conclusion

The results of the hypothesis show that there is diversity in the conclusion of the assessment. Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that there are four accepted hypotheses, while the other three are rejected. The first hypothesis is accepted: service quality has a direct and significant effect on satisfaction. Thus, the quality of services provided by Shopee will affect the level of user satisfaction. While the second hypothesis is accepted, service quality has a significant direct effect on trust. Thus, the quality of Shopee's services can affect and even increase the trust of its users. The third hypothesis is rejected, which does not directly affect the perceived value of trust. So that the perceived value (perceived value) by users cannot affect the trust of other users who intend to make purchases or shop using Shopee. The fourth hypothesis is accepted: perceived value has a direct and significant effect on loyalty. Thus, the value perceived by users can influence and even increase their loyalty to always shop or continue to use Shopee social media. The fifth hypothesis is rejected, which has no direct effect on satisfaction with WOM. So, positive satisfaction may not necessarily make them want to promote Shopee to other people through word of mouth. This is also in line with the sixth hypothesis which was also rejected, namely that trust has no direct effect on WOM. So, positive user trust may not necessarily make them want to promote Shopee to other people through word of mouth. Whereas, the seventh hypothesis is accepted: loyalty has a direct and significant effect on WOM. Thus, user loyalty makes them want to do promotions to other people by word of mouth.

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